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Levelling the Field: A Guide to an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem

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Tool 1

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Inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystem – fantasy or near future?

If you were asked to think of a typical tech entrepreneur, quite often it is a white American man such as Steve Jobs, Jeff Bezos, Elon Musk, and Mark Zuckerberg that spring to mind. These men are often portrayed as the super-heroes of our time, embodied in heroic narratives such as those associated with masculine risk taking, large sums of money and grandiose tech projects – from the digitalization of social interaction to the colonization of Mars. The fact that they are all white men is often taken for granted. Even though there are many successful female tech entrepreneurs out there¹, they are rarely being elevated in the same way as their male counterparts. This mirrors how entrepreneurship is gendered and indeed not inclusive. The entrepreneurial ecosystem is not an equal playing field.²

This guidebook emphasises the need for an ecosystem approach to create inclusive entrepreneurship. We refer to entrepreneurial ecosystems as a “combination of social, political and cultural elements within a region that support the development and growth of innovative startups and encourage nascent entrepreneurs and other actors to take the risks of starting, funding, and otherwise assisting high-risk ventures.”³ This means that entrepreneurship ecosystems involve several interconnected elements such as a conducive culture, the availability of financing, the acquisition and development of human capital, new markets for products and services, and a range of institutional and infrastructural supports.⁴ These factors are mutually reinforcing and facilitate innovation and the growth of entrepreneurship. Furthermore, these elements are by their very nature dynamic, with actors and institutions interdependent, in that they are influenced by, and in turn influence, their particular entrepreneurship ecosystem, and in so doing determine the “who”, “where” and “when” of entrepreneurship.⁵ It is common practice to think of diverse ecosystems to include a variety of businesses and industries, and system participants (e.g., stakeholders) as well as business models supporting organizations and growth orientation of ventures,⁶ not just the entrepreneurs themselves. Indeed, to succeed in building sustainable entrepreneurial environments, there is a need for engagement with the entrepreneurs themselves as the entrepreneur plays a central role in creating, maintaining, and developing the ecosystem.⁷

¹ Barnet, 2021

² Ahl & Marlow, 2012

³ Spigel 2017, p. 50

⁴ Stam, 2015

⁵ Welter, 2011

⁶ Roundy et al., 2017

⁷ Spigel, 2017; Spigel & Harrison, 2018

In this guidebook, we include the actors and factors that we believe matter for making entrepreneurship ecosystems more inclusive.⁸ A key part of the problem is that dominant stereotypes still portray the entrepreneur as a white, male, middle-class heterosexual tech genius.⁹ Such stereotypes and norms thus serve to influence the development and assessments of business ideas, with the potential risk of “missing out” on opportunities for business or leading to less efficient business innovation and creation. Ideally, tech entrepreneurial ecosystems should spur entrepreneurial activities and the success of the venture should not be determined by stereotypes but rather be based on effort, energy and creativity and be available to all regardless of social characteristics such as gender, ethnicity, religion, age, or class.¹⁰

⁸ Stam, 2015; Welter, 2011

⁹ Mellström, Balkmar & Callerstig (forthcoming)

¹⁰ For studies on this, see Broadbridge & Simpson, 2011

Today, research has convincingly demonstrated that women are underrepresented in entrepreneurial ecosystems, and a persistent gender bias continues to exist in entrepreneurship discourse and practice, affecting who gets supported in, and by, the system.¹¹ The success and failure of inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystems depends upon the potential for change of a variety of gendered processes that create and maintain inequalities: this includes considering the gendered nature of concepts such as ‘technology’, ‘innovation’, ‘innovator’, ‘entrepreneur’ and how supporting structures associated with funding and incubation matters for entrepreneurship¹² (described further in *Tool 2: The Gendered Nature of Tech Entrepreneurship*, see below). An inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystem challenges gendered privileges and inequalities, including how control over resources are gendered – typically dispersed across centres of power and controlled by some men and some forms of masculinity.¹³ These gendered relations can hinder change if those in power are not inclined or motivated to challenge the status quo. The promotion of change will thus require devotion and engagement.

About the guidebook

This guidebook addresses the gender divide in entrepreneurship to inspire actions for change. Its overall aim therefore is to promote inclusive entrepreneurship from an ecosystem perspective, emphasising that the ecosystem consists of a variety of important players, whose joint effort is needed in order to achieve change. The guidebook focuses particularly on gender in technology entrepreneurship, which includes women’s and men’s technology entrepreneurship in different national contexts. We also consider intersectional aspects of inequalities, i.e., women and men in all their diversity.

Why is inclusiveness important?

Inclusiveness also refers to inclusive innovation, potential consumers and users of products and services that entrepreneurs develop. Hence, inclusive entrepreneurship and ecosystems are important for diversity of perspectives. Serious concerns have been raised in recent years about the inability of companies to recognize different customer needs in the development of new services and products. Namely, the services and products produced and sold may only be appropriate for a small cohort of potential users, which may serve to reproduce stereotypes about both users and usage. Noteworthy examples include the smart watch that does not function on dark skin, machine learning algorithms that makes women invisible or designs that severely

¹¹ McAdam et al., 2019; McAdam, 2022

¹² Marlow & McAdam, 2012, 2015

¹³ Hearn et al. eds., 2019

limit accessibility for users with different bodily functionalities. At the centre of developing awareness of how norms affect these processes of innovation and entrepreneurship is the analysis of the reproduction of men and masculinities as the norm¹⁴, including how such norms may be challenged in ecosystem processes and outcomes.

The ecosystem approach to inclusive tech entrepreneurship we outline in this guidebook suggests that it is important to have a communicated and accepted aim and vision, preferably one that makes clear why achieving inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems is important. Below 10 reasons to promote inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems are summarized – that we hope will inspire further discussion:

Figure 1. 10 reasons to promote inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems

1. Inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems enable equal opportunities for entrepreneurship actors to contribute to societal and economic development.
2. Inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems ensure that innovations reflect the needs and experiences of a wider group of users.
3. Inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems create a bigger pool of competence and abilities needed to enable business creation and growth.
4. By working together actors in an ecosystem have a better chance of achieving their goals.
5. By ensuring transparency and equal opportunities, legitimacy and support for the ecosystem grows amongst external actors and stakeholders.
6. By ensuring transparency and equal opportunities, support from customers grows.
7. Inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems make ecosystems more competitive.
8. Inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems create better value for investments.
9. Inclusive entrepreneurship creates better work environments in companies.
10. A fair and inclusive tech entrepreneurship ecosystem is crucial to meet future societal challenges and is a vital part of achieving social sustainability.

To achieve inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems many actors, need to collaborate and work towards a sustainable societal development. This guidebook will unpack the actors involved, their roles and the processes needed to achieve a more inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystem, hopefully in a not-so-distant future.

¹⁴ Mellström, Balkmar & Callerstig (forthcoming)

Who is the guidebook intended for?

The intended target audiences for the guidebook are primarily equality strategists and other actors who have the ambition, mandate and responsibility to promote inclusion either in their own organisation or towards a wider group of ecosystem actors. We address actors working to achieve change, ranging from entrepreneurs themselves, to policy makers and people working within funding agencies and incubators in the ecosystem.

How to use the guidebook

This Guide is part of a three-part toolbox:

1. *Levelling the field: A Guide to an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem* provides a basic understanding of *how to promote* inclusive entrepreneurship from an ecosystem perspective.
2. *The Gendered Nature of Tech Entrepreneurship: Understanding the Gender-Divide in Tech Entrepreneurship* is about “the what and whys” related to gender and entrepreneurship, with a particular focus on tech entrepreneurship.
3. *My Better Entrepreneurship Ecosystem: A Workshop on How to Promote an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem* provides a format to enhance knowledge, ability and collaboration in an ecosystem focusing on *norm-reflexive ability for change* among actors in the ecosystem.

These three tools are meant as complementary components to inspire change. With the (1) guidebook providing a basic understanding of *how to promote* inclusive entrepreneurship, (2) a more theoretical publication that provides deeper *insights into different aspects of gender and inclusion*, and (3) a workshop that provides a *format and methods* to enhance knowledge, ability, and collaboration in the ecosystem.

This guidebook provides some basic facts and findings on existing challenges, suggestions for strategies and approaches on how to deal with the challenges. The more hands-on sections are followed by short summaries and key reflection points that can be used for discussions on how to make your entrepreneurial ecosystem more inclusive. In Tool 3, the workshop instruction, we also include real examples taken from the four countries in the GENRE project, which we refer to as the *Better Stories of Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystems*.

Gendering tech entrepreneurship

In this section, we introduce how tech entrepreneurship is gendered from different, yet overlapping perspectives, concerning key aspects such as innovation and funding opportunities.

First, some facts:

- Women constitute only between 5-15% of technology entrepreneurs within Europe and register a fraction of patents for innovative products and processes.¹⁵
- Despite increasing numbers of appropriately qualified women, relatively few achieve seniority within formal careers and even fewer become entrepreneurs.¹⁶

This may be unsurprising given that technology, engineering, and machinery are inherently embedded with masculinity, which is key to understanding gendered power relations.¹⁷ The relationship between gender and **technology** is crucial to understanding gender relations and how power operates to privilege men and masculinity.¹⁸ Since early on, studies on gender and technology have been concerned with women's exclusion from technical skills and careers – a perspective that has evolved into an analysis of the reproduction of the masculine character of technology itself, of fighting technological determinism and the exclusion

Gender and **entrepreneurship** are in a similar way tightly interlinked with men and masculinity. Entrepreneurial discourse is rooted in masculinity and thus privileges men and masculinity as the normative standard.²⁰ Women represent about 50% of the working-age population worldwide but are underrepresented in all forms of entrepreneurship. The yearly "Missing Entrepreneurs" reports (published by the European Commission and OECD since 2014) examine how targeted public policies can help to overcome obstacles to start-ups and self-employment to promote gender equality. The reports describe how the underrepresentation of women is due to factors such as institutional barriers, discrimination related difficulties to accessing resources, skill gaps etc. Indeed, women are often excluded from important networks, and face barriers when attempting to access resources necessary to start a business. Exclusion is often based on the 'disconfirmation of gender role expectations' manifested in

¹⁵ e.g., WIPO, 2021

¹⁶ Marlow & McAdam, 2015

¹⁷ Wajcman 1991, 2004; Faulkner 2001; Mellström, 2004

¹⁸ Cockburn, 2009; Faulkner 2001; Mellström, 2002; Wajcman, 2004

¹⁹ Wajcman, 2004

²⁰ Marlow & Martinez Dy, 2018, p. 3; Ahl, 2006

gender stereotypes. Gender is embedded in the processes, experiences, and consequences of entrepreneurship.

Also, in the **innovation** domain, male dominated, and masculine areas of knowledge are generally emphasized, while innovations in areas associated with femininity and woman dominated sectors (such as the service sector) are considered less innovative.²¹ In addition, and accordingly, women entrepreneurs are often offered inferior **funding** conditions.²² Research has shown that women entrepreneurs obtain less capital compared to men even when they have the same potential,²³ particularly when seeking venture capital.²⁴ However, there are no simple explanations to the prevailing gender gap in financing²⁵ and it is especially puzzling that access to capital still differs between men and women entrepreneurs in countries, including countries with a reputation of being gender equal, such as in the Nordic countries. In-depth gender analysis may help to pose new questions and perspectives across all these gendered dimensions, enabling us to challenge norms and develop better stories than the current ones.

²¹ Lindberg, 2018

²² Mascia & Rossi, 2017

²³ Alsos et al. 2006, Malmström et al. 2018

²⁴ Brush et al. 2019

²⁵ Leitch et al. 2018

Facts & Figures

In most countries, according to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) Global report 2020/2021, new businesses are more likely to be started by men than by women. Even though there are a handful of economies where the level of female entrepreneurship is higher, overall, the gender gap is persistent.²⁶ Almost all countries have more entrepreneurship among men compared to women. Against this background, to achieve a more inclusive and gender equal entrepreneurship ecosystem would be of great benefit to societies across the globe.

Typically, women take on more family responsibilities than their male partners²⁷ and therefore the institutional environment in terms of a country's family provision institutional arrangements influences women's engagement and participation in entrepreneurship activities.²⁸ Women entrepreneurship is also impacted by the rates of gender discrimination and labour market policies as well as access to relevant education, business ownership and capital.²⁹ Country data collected in the GENRE project illustrates the differences between countries (presented in Table 2) and highlights the paradox that even in seemingly gender equal countries there are significant gaps in entrepreneurial activity.

Table 2: Country Data Related to Gender Issues (Heilbrunn et al., 2020)

	Ireland	Norway	Sweden	Israel
Gender Equality Index³⁰ (2018) rank of 149	9	2	3	46
Women Labour Force Participation³¹ (2018)	56%	60.4%	61.4%	59.7%
Share of Women in Parliament³² (2019)	24.3%	40.8%	47.1%	23.3%
Gender Wage Gap³³	5.9%	7.1%	7.3%	21.8%
Female science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) Graduates³⁴	24.8%	19.3%	22.4%	24.8%

²⁶ GEM 2020/2021, p. 54

²⁷ Oláh et al., 2018

²⁸ McAdam, 2013

²⁹ Foss et al., 2019

³⁰ <http://reports.weforum.org/global-gender-gap-report-2018/data-explorer/#economy=NOR>

³¹ <http://hdr.undp.org/en/content/table-5-gender-inequality-index-gii>

³² <http://hdr.undp.org/en/composite/GII>

³³ <https://www.oecd.org/gender/data/employment/>

³⁴ <https://www.honeypot.io/women-in-tech-2018/>

Women in Entrepreneurship Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) TEA³⁵	7.5%	5.1%	4.0%	9.1%
Share of Women Investors (2017)³⁶	9.6%	9.0%	7.3%	12.2%
Women in High-Tech Sector³⁷	18.9%	19.4%	20.8%	11.0 %
Maternity related issues				
Length of maternity leave/parental leave	26 weeks ³⁸	49–59 weeks (including 16–19 weeks paternity leave)	68 weeks ³⁹	15 weeks (105 days) ⁴⁰
	Ireland	Norway	Sweden	Israel
Financial support during maternity leave	Maternity Benefit ⁴¹	80% of salary (59 weeks) or 100% salary (49 weeks)	80% of previous income 6 month before birth	The same income as before giving birth
State subsidised child-care facilities from age	2.8 ⁴²	9-14 months	1 year	3 years
Average monthly cost of pre-school/kindergartens	€736 ⁴³	€270), less for siblings	€140, less for siblings	3000 NIS (about €750)

³⁵ [https://www.gemconsortium.org/report/gem-20182019-womens-entrepreneurship-report;](https://www.gemconsortium.org/report/gem-20182019-womens-entrepreneurship-report) for Norway <https://www.gemconsortium.org/economy-profiles/norway-2>

³⁶ <https://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx?queryid=54676>

³⁷ <https://www.honeypot.io/women-in-tech-2018/>

³⁸ https://www.citizensinformation.ie/en/employment/employment_rights_and_conditions/leave_and_holidays/parental_leave.html

³⁹ 90 days cannot be transferred to the other parent, often referred to as 3 reserved ‘daddy months’.

⁴⁰ National Insurance Institute of Israel

<https://www.btl.gov.il/English%20homepage/Pages/default.aspx>

⁴¹ https://www.citizensinformation.ie/en/social_welfare/social_welfare_payments/social_welfare_payments_to_families_and_children/maternity_benefit.html

⁴² https://www.citizensinformation.ie/en/education/pre_school_education_and_childcare/early_childhood_care_and_education_scheme.html

⁴³ <https://www.irishtimes.com/news/ireland/irish-news/childcare-costs-parents-in-dublin-pay-70-more-on-average-1.4031837>

The Gender Equality Index (GEI) is a composite indicator that measures the complex concept of gender equality in several core domains such as work, money, knowledge, time, power, and health. Israel is ranked lowest among the four countries with Ireland, Sweden and Norway all ranked in the top ten countries on gender equality. The ranking order reflects other comparative data, such as the wage gap and the share of women in parliament in each of the four countries. The data shows that Israel has the highest percentage of female investors, but at the same time, the lowest percentage of women working in the high-tech sector. Country differences were also found in relation to childcare facilities, which in practice play a critical role in supporting or constraining female entrepreneurship.⁴⁴

Data from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM), and national official data, can be used to further specify gender (im)balance among entrepreneurs across the four studied countries Ireland, Israel, Norway, and Sweden. For example, among early-stage entrepreneurs, there are 1.8 men for every female early-stage entrepreneur in Ireland.⁴⁵ In Israel, the total early-stage entrepreneurial activity amounts to about 10% for men and 8% for women.⁴⁶ In Norway, the total early-stage entrepreneurial activity amounts to about 10% for men and 5% for women.⁴⁷ The total early-stage entrepreneurial activity in Sweden amounts to about 10% for men and 5% for women.⁴⁸ For venture capital funding similar gender patterns apply. Even though data may be fragmented, they give the indication that women entrepreneurs receive a very small share of funding. Irish data on women's share of venture capital funding demonstrates that the funding for female founders of tech start-ups fell to 6% in the first half of 2021, even though the overall investment in Irish tech companies reached a record €932 million.⁴⁹ For Israel, the share of women's venture capital funding amounts to 2%. Most of the venture capital raised by entrepreneurial teams in Norway goes to all-male teams, raising 80 % of the total amount, 18 % of capital raised goes to mixed teams, and only 2 % goes to all-female teams.⁵⁰ For Sweden, extensive data is lacking, some argue that women's share of venture capital funding is one percent, even less if immigrant background is considered.⁵¹

⁴⁴ Welter, 2004

⁴⁵ GEM Ireland 2019, <https://www.gemconsortium.org/report/gem-ireland-2019-report>

⁴⁶ GEM 2020/2021 Global Report

⁴⁷ GEM 2020/2021 Global Report

⁴⁸ GEM 2020/2021 Global Report

⁴⁹ Enterprise Ireland, 2020

⁵⁰ Unconventional Ventures, 2019

⁵¹ <https://www.di.se/debatt/riskkapitalet-maste-aven-na-kvinnorna/>

The findings from the GENRE project show how gendered contexts matter for the gender divide visible in technology entrepreneurship in each of the countries investigated. Differences are reflected in policies to promote gender equality in technology entrepreneurship. Yet, the prevailing strong masculinized norms in entrepreneurship that are visible in all countries studied are not fully addressed in the gender policies in entrepreneurship which are mainstream in their content. Policies thus need to go beyond focusing on the “missing women” to address the masculinized norms in tech entrepreneurship and men’s role in achieving gender equality.⁵²

⁵² Callerstig et al. 2022

Promoting inclusive (tech) entrepreneurship – the Ecosystem Approach

There are a multitude of different factors that determine the inclusivity of entrepreneurship.⁵³ Inclusiveness is, as described earlier, dependent on factors that range from structural conditions such as social safety-nets and societal gender relations, to everyday relational aspects, such as the gendered division of care work. Legal framework and gender equality objectives and policies have an important role in promoting a more inclusive entrepreneurship.

As already noted in the introduction, also the entrepreneur plays a central role in creating, maintaining, and developing the ecosystem and not just responding to its pressures and opportunities.⁵⁴ Other entrepreneurial actors of importance can be found in various organisations such as incubators and investor organisations and are all part of the larger system of the ecosystem.

To achieve change, one cannot focus on one level, organisation, or actor in isolation, since all play a part in achieving a more inclusive ecosystem. Apart from the entrepreneurs themselves, organisational level actors and system level actors make up ecosystem stakeholders that can make a difference individually and as collective efforts. The individual entrepreneur and individual start-ups also form their own organisation, where inclusion is a key aspect for attracting, retaining, and facilitating fruitful collaborations with key actors, all important for starting and growing a business.

How can entrepreneurship ecosystems become more inclusive?

In this guidebook, we focus on how more inclusive ecosystems can be achieved by intentionally initiated and coordinated actions through cooperation between ecosystem actors. This is done to achieve a more harmonised approach and to avoid mitigate against the actions by one actor will having potential negative effects on the possibilities to promote inclusiveness by other actors.

We call this the ***ecosystem approach*** to inclusive technical entrepreneurship. Below, we describe why we believe this to be important in achieving transformation.

⁵³ See Welter 2020 for a recent discussion on research on the gendered context of entrepreneurship

⁵⁴ Spigel, 2017

The ecosystem approach for inclusive entrepreneurship entails:

1. **Acknowledgment that entrepreneurship ecosystems involve several interconnected elements** such as a conducive culture, the availability of financing, the acquisition and development of human capital, new markets for products and services, and a range of institutional and infrastructural supports, which are mutually reinforcing and facilitate innovation and the growth of entrepreneurship.
2. **Acknowledgment of the role of the entrepreneurs** in creating, maintaining, and developing the ecosystem and not just responding to its pressures and opportunities. The entrepreneur plays a central role in creating, maintaining, and developing the ecosystem. Ecosystems influence and are influenced by the entrepreneurs themselves.
3. The ecosystem approach **sheds light on the key players, power positions, and power struggles**. Therefore, allyship and lobbying may be mechanisms in which to improve positions and minimize power struggles and inequalities. This holistic approach necessitates the inclusion of all actors in the whole ecosystems as relevant for achieving a more inclusive ecosystem, no matter what 'power position' the actor has within the ecosystem.
4. The ecosystem approach **emphasises a holistic approach for working with the underlying reasons for gender gaps**. It is an approach that challenges all actors to reflect on gender norms, including addressing how norms often are taken for granted. The holistic approach includes multi-level, multi-stakeholder and multi-methodology towards more inclusive entrepreneurship.
5. If an ecosystem approach is taken to **highlight all the benefits that come with increased gender equality** – the focus will be that not only women can benefit, if women and other underrepresented groups are given equal opportunities to participate in tech entrepreneurship, but rather the benefit for society as a whole.

Building on the above we recommend:

- To promote the ecosystem as a **built-in network facilitator** for inclusive entrepreneurship, and;
- To engage in **education and awareness-raising** amongst different stakeholders in the ecosystem about the interconnectedness of ecosystem elements and (in)equalities in doing so.
- Promote and enforce **allyship** amongst both male and female actors in the ecosystem, particularly at the grassroots level, to empower entrepreneurs to play an active role in creating, maintaining, and developing the entrepreneurial ecosystem.
- Ensure broad participation of ecosystem actors and a **holistic approach** to avoid a patch-work approach in the work to promote inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems.
- Support mechanisms to promote **grass-root activity** and learning such as the establishment of networking hubs and use of virtual spaces such as social media to create collaborative interest.
- Revise **attitudes towards care and improve childcare provision services** across all different levels of the society: individual, organizational and ecosystem level, including childcare services within the incubators and engage in discussions about gender roles and labour division within the private sphere and work-life balance.
- Promote an **equal representation** among all actors of the ecosystem such as support to initiatives that aim to increase the number of female investors, business coaches and incubator tenants to promote critical mass.
- Where possible – give more room for **female role models**, for example, on webpages, commercials for incubators etc. In addition to more women role models, also include alternative “**non-stereotypical**” **male role models** (and other non-normative role models).
- Highlight and discuss **ideals and cultures** within both entrepreneurship and technology.

The approach is shown in the diagram below with key components to achieve transformation according to our research findings.

Figure 3. The ecosystem as a built-in network facilitator

The ecosystem approach requires input from individual ecosystem actors and simultaneous collaboration between actors. Before we discuss how actors can collaborate, we highlight some of the ways that central ecosystem actors can contribute.

Different ecosystem actor's role for change

Incubators: Incubators act as ecosystem intermediaries in the provision of start-up resources for founders (infrastructure and office space etc.) and by their leveraging/bridging effect with other components in the ecosystem. Incubators can also help to cultivate entrepreneurial mindsets, culture, and networks. Incubators play an important role in creating more inclusive ecosystems as they can act as a gateway to critical resources for new entrepreneurs. Gender sensitive tailoring and design of incubator programmes will help progress towards more inclusive incubation and less gender bias in the assessment and interaction with potential tenants. Incubators also play a key role in promoting inclusion through their many interactions with other ecosystem actors. (See as examples the work by incubators such as KTH Innovation and Start Up Lab in the Better stories section in the *My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem* report).

Founders: With regards to the role of founders in making the ecosystem more inclusive, female founders who are active players in the ecosystem can initiate networks aimed at assisting other women in overcoming potential obstacles and barriers. Mentorship and networks of women founders can focus on professional fields (for example medical devices, internet platforms, etc.) since expertise is a vital asset for founders. Additionally, founders can communicate gender issues to incubator management and funders to help raise awareness of the gendered aspects of tech entrepreneurship. In the GENRE project many of the interviewed founders, both male, and female were passionate about encouraging more women tech entrepreneurship and articulated the benefits that inclusion and diversity can bring to their own businesses. (See the example of Awaken Hub and "Ha'Meitzot" in *My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem report*, Tool 3)

Public actors and policy makers: Public actors and policy makers are important actors in that they can initiate specific policy measures to promote fair and inclusive ecosystems. They can also mainstream general policies to make sure they integrate an equality perspective. In many countries, public actors of various kinds act as collaborative platforms and can initiate joint processes in ecosystems. (See for example *Vinnova, Israel Innovation Authority, The Research Council of Norway, and Enterprise Ireland* in the *My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem report* Tool 3).

Collaboration in ecosystems increases the capacity for inclusive technology entrepreneurship

Summing up and key reflection points

So far, we have highlighted how inclusive entrepreneurship can be promoted on **different levels**, and we have also outlined ways that different **stakeholders** in the ecosystem can contribute. We have also introduced the benefits and challenges of **collaboration**, including which **necessary steps** to take.

In the following section, before we move on to discuss the practical work to promote change in more detail, we ask you to reflect on the current situation in your country/ecosystem.

Key reflection points

- What are the main factors impacting on the possibilities for an inclusive tech entrepreneurship on different levels in your context?
- What would you say are the main challenges for inclusion in the ecosystem you are part of and how are they interrelated?
- Who are the central actors in your ecosystem and how have they contributed or may contribute to a more inclusive tech entrepreneurship in the future?
- How can further collaboration benefit more inclusive ecosystems?
- Around what, more specifically, can collaboration be formed? How and with what resources and potential results?

The practical work to promote change – getting the job done

To achieve a more inclusive ecosystem careful planning is needed to identify both problems to address and which strategies and actors that are most relevant to address them. In this section, we will discuss some of the key factors and measures to promote change in relation to specific challenges.

Different types of strategies

First a few words on strategies. Choice of strategy is typically dependent on what is seen as a problem or challenge to begin with, but also what goal to strive for and the best way to fulfil this goal. Together this makes up the *logic* of a strategy and sets out the desired effects, objectives, and results. In other words, based on the strategy you

can plan which activities to undertake, the resources needed to enable the activities, and the desired goals.

We have identified both short term and long-term strategies, those that are aimed at influencing *internal* conditions and those directed towards other *organizations* or *citizens*. Strategies may target a single problem or have a more holistic or multi-problem approach. Strategies can be geared to promote equality in many ways and with different aims. Sometimes the aim is to ensure equal treatment of all, sometimes they seek to promote equality through specific affirmative measures, and sometimes they aim to disrupt more underlying structures and norms. Often a mixture of different types of strategies and tools are used by successful actors.

No quick fix - rather trial and error!

Modern day research shows that there is no easy or quick-fix model for achieving inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystems. The roots to inequality are complex. We suggest an approach where attention is given to the change logic underlying different types of strategies and tools and to see strategies as complementary rather than mutually exclusive. This allows for a continuous assessment, learning and adjustment of initiatives undertaken. We suggest paying close attention to whether specific aims are reached by the measures applied or if they need to adapt as the process evolves. Therefore, flexibility in change processes is key and resultant adjustment to both aims and measures the norm.

The exchange of experiences and learning from both initiatives undertaken as well as from the voices of marginalised groups of entrepreneurs is a fruitful way to promote transformation. Co-creative methods in designing initiatives are important to get a good sense of what could be fruitful action to take and to ensure both engagement and commitment to the development work.

We have developed two co-creative practical tools - *personas* and *better stories* - that can assist in understanding both the challenges faced by marginalized entrepreneurs and how initiatives to promote a higher level of inclusion can be undertaken. (See the tool to create a collaborative workshop *My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem*).

- **Personas:** We have developed several *personas* to spur reflections and discussions with regards to norms and unconscious bias related to entrepreneurship. Personas are archetypes of tech entrepreneurs designed to initiate discussions and inspire to address specific problems that the persona faces.
- **Better stories:** We have also collected “better stories” from four countries. Better stories refer to inspiring examples of working with promoting (gender) inclusiveness in tech entrepreneurship. “Better” captures not the “best way to

solve a particular challenge in a normative or definite sense, but rather, what is possible at a particular moment.⁵⁸ Better stories are not a search for a “perfect fix for all” but an invitation to identify, highlight and learn from the better stories to create more inclusive ecosystems emerging from different contexts, as well as an invitation to imagine even better stories to be further developed.

These tools can be used in the suggested complementary workshop for actors in the ecosystem on how to create “better” and more inclusive ecosystems for entrepreneurship and can be a good start for future collaborations and exchanges.

Ensuring favourable conditions

In the following section, advice is given on what we have identified as success factors for initiatives to have the desired effect. As the leader of a change initiative, four conditions to ensure favourable conditions have been deemed important in earlier research:⁵⁹

1. Ensure there is a willingness to question and effectively address the often deeply rooted structures of power, gender hierarchies and values.
2. Ensure to approach implementation as a phased process including a thorough analysis that precedes the planning and definition of actions, followed by the careful and comprehensive equipping of all actors (with tools and resources), and duly monitored implementation.
3. Ensure consultation with and involvement of civil society and/or experts.
4. Ensure proper accountability structures and systems are in place.

What do founders want?

In the GENRE project, founders, both male and female were interviewed about their individual and experiences and opinions with regards how a more inclusive ecosystem could be achieved. Both male and female founders reported upon existing inequalities and ways to support inclusiveness. Below is a “wish list” and a summary of what the founders identified as important for inclusive ecosystems.

- To be included as an entrepreneur on equal terms without becoming a token or “made different”
- To have a fair and unbiased assessment of entrepreneurial skills and business ideas
- To pay attention to other factors besides gender that influence the opportunities for different groups of entrepreneurs such as age and ethnical origin

⁵⁸ Georgis, 2013., p.2

⁵⁹ Mergaert, 2012

- To address underlying norms and gendered stereotypes of technology entrepreneurship
- To take part in and discuss entrepreneurship from everyday realities, not only through success or heroic stories
- Leaders and policy makers express a strong will to promote inclusive entrepreneurship and are actively engaged in advocating the need for transformation
- To have the possibility to combine entrepreneurship with family responsibilities
- Men as allies. Men need to support women and gender equality to promote inclusiveness

Problems and solutions

We now turn to specific problems and solutions that are likely to be addressed to achieve inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems. First, we would like to stress the importance of three overarching and interlinked values to be considered when thinking about addressing problems and solutions – *diversity*, *inclusion*, and *equality* (see Figure 5 below). Together, they form the basis of all work towards change that the ecosystem actors may do, individually and together.

Figure 5. *Diversity, Inclusion, Equality – links and connections*

The figure above teases out the differences and links between the concepts *Diversity*, *Inclusion* and *Equality*. While **diversity** is about recognizing, respecting, and valuing *differences* in people, **equality** is a concept that stresses the importance of *equal opportunities* and protecting people (with all their ‘differences’) from being discriminated against. Lastly, **inclusion** refers to individuals’ *experiences* within the workplace and in wider society, and the extent to which a person feels valued and

included. The efforts to achieve change can be designed and assessed by considering if and how they contribute to reaching all these approaches.

On a more detailed level, there are a variety of approaches that actors may work with in an ecosystem. Examples of such approaches are summed up in the table below highlighting which problem they address, and the strategies and tools applied. Note that the same tools can be used for different problems identified and with different strategic aims. The table consists of suggestions and is by no means exhaustive. We hope that it will be used to structure further discussions and as inspiration for idea creation.

Figure 6. Commonly suggested problems and tools for inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems

Problems to be addressed	Strategies (examples)	Tools (examples)
Women do not see themselves as tech entrepreneurs	Encourage women to become entrepreneurs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Role models - Communication strategies - Mentoring, see the <i>AwakenHub</i>, <i>Supersonas/Hameizot</i>
Prevailing gendered stereotypes of who is or can become a tech entrepreneur	Change norms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share examples and stories of women, ethnic minorities etc. as entrepreneurs - Stating a declaration to increase/invite women e.g., Women are welcome - Businesses with an explicit aim to include more women in tech, see <i>Enterprise Ireland</i> - Outreach activities from ecosystem actors towards education - Collaborate with universities that provides education business and technology courses, See <i>KTH and Gender Contact point</i>
Implicit gender bias in assessing individual and business potentials and capabilities in the entrepreneurship process	Measures to detect and address implicit gender bias	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equal validation systems - Bias training - Set targets and monitor gender representation of candidates, see <i>VINNOVA</i>
Equality is not promoted by all actors - only some, or only some problems addressed	Ensure holistic approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration between actors - Multi-problem and horizontal approaches, see <i>VINNOVA</i>
Homosocial practices that keep women and other minorities out (i.e., Old boys club)	Ensuring equal access to actors and resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Women specific network, see <i>Supersonas</i> - Men as mentors - Grants for Female-led Start-ups, see <i>Israel Innovation Authority</i>
Equality defined as a women's problem	Broadening the understanding of inclusive entrepreneurship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage men - Apply intersectional perspectives - Include experts and gender researchers in the field, see <i>Gender Contact Point</i>

Problem of reconciling entrepreneurship with care responsibilities	Measures to promote care sensitive entrepreneurship	- Flexible business hours in incubators - Inclusive working environments
Limited awareness of existing gender and other types of inequalities	Increase awareness	- Communication/information efforts - Gender mainstreaming in educational curriculum - Gender training for ecosystem actors
Actors do not work systematically and proactively to address inequalities	Systematic and pro-active organisational work	- Start-ups include equality aspects, see <i>Startup lab</i> - Funders demand equality plans
Actors do not work in a unified way, contradictory work between actors in ecosystem	Strengthen collaboration between actors	- Collaborative initiatives, see <i>Research Council of Norway, Gender Contact Point</i>

The table consists of examples of approaches in use in the countries included in the GENRE project. Some initiatives are also represented in the section called Better stories in the workshop instruction *My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem* – to guide readers that want to dig deeper into how to promote inclusive entrepreneurship.

Summing up and key reflection points

In this section, we have stressed many aspects of the practical work such as the importance of having a communicated and accepted aim and vision about why an inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystem is needed. We have addressed the need for a balanced and complementary approach with attention to the overlapping values of diversity, inclusion, and equality. We have highlighted what leaders need to do to ensure favourable conditions in their respective organisations. By doing this, a common ground and potential for collaboration and co-creation is established for which we have listed ideas on how to proceed. We have also listed specific problems, strategies and solutions, and tools to consider when working to achieve inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystems.

Key reflection points:

- Looking at the founders “wish list”, what problems are important to address in our ecosystem and how can different actors contribute to change?
- What strategies and solutions do you believe to be most effective and why?
- How can different strategies and solutions complement each other?
- How can favourable conditions to support the work for change be ensured in your own organisation?

Finally...

Every journey starts with a small step, and we wish you good luck on your path towards more inclusive tech entrepreneurship ecosystems.

The GENRE research team

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GENRE is a three-year research project that aims to investigate and cross-culturally compare the lived experiences of female technology entrepreneurs in incubation and investing ecosystems in four different countries. The findings generated inform policy development aimed at inclusivity and sustainability, thus benefiting both women and men. It is a transnational research project taking place simultaneously in Ireland (Dublin City University), Norway (Nord University), Sweden (Karlstad and Örebro University) and Israel (Kinneret College). The project is coordinated by DCU Business School (Dublin) and led by Prof Maura McAdam. GENRE is co-funded under the GENDER-NET Plus Joint Call Grant Number GNP-122.

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